

CULTiVATE

A Summary Report of 105 FSI Landscapes

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Overview

3052	Food Sharing Initiatives
105	European urban and peri-urban areas were mapped
2226	Initiatives are redistributing food, saving surplus food from disposal and providing food for those in need
834	Initiatives are cooking and eating together, reducing loneliness and improving nutrition
1195	Initiatives are growing food, reducing spend on food for participants and creating opportunities for enhancing physical and mental wellbeing
985	Initiatives undertake multiple activities around food, contributing to a circular bioeconomy

The Food Sharing Map will be launched in February 2026. It will support policymakers, municipalities, local FSIs, practitioners, and citizens by showing the food sharing activities taking place in their area.

<https://www.sharingsolutions.eu/food-sharing-map>

CULTIVATE Food Sharing Mapping

FSI Category ● Cooking & Eating ● Distribution ● Growing ● Multifunctional

Data collection process

The data search was carried out in six rounds: one manual mapping round for the 12 test cities in 2024, followed by five automated rounds covering all 105 cities in 2025. In 2024, the three hub cities—Milan, Utrecht and Barcelona—were mapped more intensively over a three-month period. Repeated rounds enabled the identification of initiatives missed earlier and helped maintain consistency across cities. As the dataset approached saturation, the number of newly identified FSIs declined in the later rounds.

Food sharing activities

Distribution is the most common activity among the mapped FSIs. However, many initiatives work across more than one activity area. Collective cooking and eating in particular is likely to be combined with other activities. Around 67% of cooking and eating initiatives also engage in areas such as food distribution or growing. In contrast, a comparatively large share of food distribution initiatives (57%) operate solely in distribution.

What mode of sharing is used?

Gifting is the most common mode of sharing among FSIs. Several initiatives use more than one approach, combining methods such as selling small amounts of food, collecting surplus items, or bartering within their communities. These mixed practices indicate that food sharing often relies on a blend of monetary and non-monetary exchanges rather than a single, uniform model.

Three Hub Cities: Milan, Utrecht, and Barcelona

For the three hub cities—Milan, Utrecht and Barcelona—the CULTIVATE project produced comparable datasets for 2024 and 2025. In 2024, these cities were mapped manually. In 2025, the automated mapping tool re-mapped them five additional times. FSIs already identified in 2024 were removed from the 2025 results, allowing us to isolate only newly detected initiatives.

Across the hub cities, the 2025 searches identified 282 additional FSIs. However, this increase does not necessarily signal the emergence of new initiatives. Only a small number were genuinely new. Most were long-established organisations, such as churches or nationwide charities, that did not appear in the 2024 mapping because they were not actively engaged in food sharing at that time. Their activities became more visible in 2025, often through new campaigns or events, making them detectable by the automated tool.

Compared with the 2024 data, cooking and eating activities also appear to increase in 2025. In line with the broader trends, this does not indicate the establishment of new FSIs but reflects shifts in how existing organisations communicated their activities online. In Utrecht in particular, long-established charities had been running social meal activities for some time, but these became more visible in 2025 through updated information, event postings and expanded public communication. As a result, the automated tool was able to detect a greater number of cooking and eating activities in 2025.

105 FSI Landscapes

Across the 105 cities included in the dataset, population size and the number of FSIs show a general trend: larger cities tend to host more initiatives. Very small cities such as Valletta, Victoria, Dudelange, Tórshavn and Koper—each with populations below 30,000—rarely have more than ten FSIs. However, this does not mean that larger cities consistently exhibit higher levels of FSI activity, and the relationship becomes less clear when all cities are considered together. Instead, the data suggests that cultural–regional clusters, such as Western, Northern, Southern and Eastern Europe, play a more decisive role in shaping the FSI landscape, even though these categories remain contextual.

The correlation between population size and the number of FSIs becomes clearer only within each regional cluster, rather than across the dataset as a whole. For example, in the Southwestern European cluster, larger cities typically display higher levels of FSI activity, showing a relatively strong internal correlation (0.60952811). By contrast, Northern European cities tend to have lower population densities and comparatively modest levels of FSI activity, weakening the overall pattern (0.5551406). Eastern European cities generally fall within a medium population range and tend to host around 20–30 FSIs, producing a different type of consistency (0.30921216, excluding Kyiv). Kyiv is excluded because the ongoing war significantly affects both population estimates and the visibility of FSIs, placing the city outside the expected pattern. Other neighbouring cities—Ankara, Auckland, Jerusalem, Rabat, Tbilisi, Tunis and Yerevan—also lack sufficient comparable data to establish reliable trends and do not align with broader European patterns.

Clusters	Correlation between FSIs and Population	FSIs per 100,000 inhabitants
105 cities	0.250696462	6.96
Southwestern European cluster	0.60952811	12.29
Northern European cluster	0.5551406	3.88
Eastern European cluster (excluding Kyiv)	0.30921216	4.70

When examining total FSIs relative to total population, Southern and Western European cities show the highest levels of activity, reaching 12.29 FSIs per 100,000 inhabitants. Even when the hub cities are removed—cities that received additional manual mapping support—the regional trend remains similar, with 10.49 FSIs per 100,000 inhabitants. Northern Europe shows lower levels of activity overall (3.88), while Eastern Europe remains moderate (4.70, excluding Kyiv).

The overall visibility of FSIs may still reflect structural differences in local food-policy and civic environments. Southern and Western European cities, in particular, tend to have long-established civic infrastructures, strong food-culture networks and higher levels of online documentation, with many initiatives maintaining formal websites or participating in public-facing policy frameworks such as the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact. These conditions not only make their activities more easily identifiable through automated tools, but also mirror the contexts in which the CULTIVATE Dictionary was initially developed and validated.

Although we made deliberate efforts to minimise such regional biases—by working with local-language speakers, iteratively refining the CULTIVATE Food Sharing Dictionary, validating classifications with hub cities and manually reviewing ambiguous cases—the optimisation and verification processes may still align more closely with the institutional and cultural environments of Southern and Western Europe, as most test cases were situated in these regions. As a result, higher identification rates in these areas may partly reflect differences in digital visibility and policy infrastructures, rather than solely the actual prevalence of food-sharing initiatives.

The figure shows all 105 mapped cities, with font size indicating the number of FSIs in each location. As large cities that were involved in manual mapping of FSIs to build the automated mapping tool Barcelona, Utrecht, Milan, and Lyon stand out with the highest counts.

This figure uses font size to indicate the number of FSIs per capita. Unlike the previous figure, medium-sized Western European cities tend to stand out more.

Summary

This report presents an overview of 3,052 Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs) across 105 European urban and peri-urban areas, mapped through a combination of manual and automated searches conducted between 2024 and 2025. The resulting Sharing Solutions Food Sharing Map, to be launched in January 2026, provides a unique resource for policymakers, municipalities, practitioners and citizens by illustrating the diversity of food sharing practices taking place in their local areas.

Food distribution is the most common activity across the mapped FSIs, followed by growing and then cooking and eating together. A large share of initiatives work across multiple activities, contributing simultaneously to social connection, improved nutrition, surplus food redistribution and local circular bioeconomies. Gifting remains the dominant mode of sharing, although many initiatives combine monetary and non-monetary approaches.

Across the 105 cities, regional context rather than population size plays a more significant role in shaping the density and visibility of FSIs. Southern and Western European cities exhibit the highest levels of activity, supported by long-established civic infrastructures and stronger public communication. The three hub cities—Milan, Utrecht and Barcelona—demonstrate how changes in online visibility, rather than the emergence of new initiatives, contributed to the identification of additional FSIs in 2025. These findings highlight the importance of recognising both structural conditions and digital visibility when interpreting patterns in urban food sharing across Europe.

Appendix: the list of 105 cities

The list is sorted by the number of identified FSIs.

City	Country	The number of identified FSIs	Regional cluster	FSIs per 100,000 population ¹
Barcelona	Spain	261	Southern Europe	19.00
Utrecht	Netherlands	198	Western Europe	61.67
Milan	Italy	163	Southern Europe	14.72
Bordeaux	France	140	Western Europe	56.54
Turin	Italy	120	Southern Europe	15.93
Lyon	France	111	Western Europe	21.96
Dublin	Republic of Ireland	83	Western Europe	7.73
Nantes	France	83	Western Europe	25.94
Brighton and Hove	United Kingdom	81	Western Europe	28.28
Marseille	France	77	Western Europe	9.51
Dresden	Germany	77	Western Europe	14.00
Bari	Italy	67	Southern Europe	20.94
Seville	Spain	65	Southern Europe	9.85
Antwerp	Belgium	61	Western Europe	11.73
Liege	Belgium	60	Western Europe	30.77
Cork	Republic of Ireland	54	Western Europe	24.55
Graz	Austria	54	Western Europe	18.62
Auckland	New Zealand	54	Other / Neighbourhood	3.86
Innsbruck	Austria	51	Western Europe	37.78
Brno	Czech Republic	51	Eastern Europe	13.42
Ljubljana	Slovenia	43	Southern Europe	14.58

¹ Population figures are based on available estimates. Official data were used where possible; otherwise, publicly accessible sources such as city-level estimates from Wikipedia were applied.

Galway	Republic of Ireland	42	Western Europe	49.41
Palermo	Italy	41	Southern Europe	6.46
Budapest	Hungary	40	Eastern Europe	2.73
The Hague	Netherlands	39	Western Europe	7.34
Athens	Greece	37	Southern Europe	5.75
Palma de Mallorca	Spain	36	Southern Europe	8.57
Linz	Austria	35	Western Europe	17.07
Jerusalem	Israel	30	Other / Neighbourhood	3.45
Wrocław	Poland	28	Eastern Europe	4.41
Pécs	Hungary	26	Eastern Europe	18.57
Aarhus	Denmark	26	Northern Europe	7.43
Limerick	Republic of Ireland	25	Western Europe	26.32
Braşov	Romania	24	Eastern Europe	9.60
Ghent	Belgium	24	Western Europe	9.06
Ostrava	Czech Republic	22	Eastern Europe	7.86
Ankara	Turkey	22	Other / Neighbourhood	0.59
Maribor	Slovenia	21	Southern Europe	19.09
Cluj-Napoca	Romania	21	Eastern Europe	6.46
Bratislava	Slovakia	20	Eastern Europe	4.65
Plzeň	Czech Republic	19	Eastern Europe	10.86
Gdańsk	Poland	19	Eastern Europe	4.04
Helsinki	Finland	19	Northern Europe	2.90
Oslo	Norway	18	Northern Europe	2.61
Braga	Portugal	17	Southern Europe	8.95
Debrecen	Hungary	17	Eastern Europe	8.50
Tartu	Estonia	16	Northern Europe	16.84

Freiberg	Germany	15	Western Europe	37.50
Bremerhaven	Germany	15	Western Europe	13.64
San Sebastián	Spain	15	Southern Europe	7.89
Aalborg	Denmark	15	Northern Europe	6.82
Lisbon	Portugal	15	Southern Europe	2.83
Chişinău	Moldova	15	Eastern Europe	2.38
Zagreb	Croatia	15	Southern Europe	2.11
Linköping	Sweden	14	Northern Europe	8.48
Malmö	Sweden	14	Northern Europe	4.00
Riga	Latvia	13	Northern Europe	2.20
Sofia	Bulgaria	13	Eastern Europe	1.18
Kyiv	Ukraine	13	Eastern Europe	0.57
Lublin	Poland	12	Eastern Europe	3.53
Plovdiv	Bulgaria	12	Eastern Europe	3.53
Košice	Slovakia	11	Eastern Europe	4.68
Faro	Portugal	10	Southern Europe	15.38
Torres Vedras	Portugal	10	Southern Europe	11.76
Kaunas	Lithuania	10	Northern Europe	3.45
Koper	Slovenia	9	Southern Europe	36.00
Split	Croatia	9	Southern Europe	5.63
Heraklion	Greece	9	Southern Europe	5.14
Tampere	Finland	9	Northern Europe	3.67
Constanța	Romania	9	Eastern Europe	3.21
Varna	Bulgaria	9	Eastern Europe	2.69
Tallinn	Estonia	9	Northern Europe	2.02
Liepāja	Latvia	8	Northern Europe	11.43
Oulu	Finland	8	Northern Europe	3.81

Nicosia	Cyprus	8	Southern Europe	2.42
Belgrade	Serbia	8	Southern Europe	0.73
Žilina	Slovakia	7	Eastern Europe	8.75
Rijeka	Croatia	7	Southern Europe	6.36
Patras	Greece	7	Southern Europe	3.26
Vilnius	Lithuania	7	Northern Europe	1.21
Kolding	Denmark	6	Northern Europe	10.00
Umeå	Sweden	6	Northern Europe	4.62
Larissa	Greece	6	Southern Europe	4.14
Klaipėda	Lithuania	6	Northern Europe	4.00
Limassol	Cyprus	6	Southern Europe	2.40
Sarajevo	Bosnia and Herzegovina	6	Southern Europe	2.18
Yerevan	Armenia	6	Other / Neighbourhood	0.63
Narva	Estonia	5	Northern Europe	9.09
Ede	Netherlands	5	Western Europe	4.17
Esch-sur-Alzette	Luxembourg	4	Western Europe	11.43
Daugavpils	Latvia	4	Northern Europe	5.00
Reykjavík	Iceland	4	Northern Europe	2.96
Tirana	Albania	4	Southern Europe	0.95
Skopje	North Macedonia	4	Southern Europe	0.73
Rabat	Morocco	3	Other / Neighbourhood	0.54
Tbilisi	Georgia	2	Other / Neighbourhood	0.19
Famagusta	Cyprus	1	Southern Europe	2.50
Luxembourg City	Luxembourg	1	Western Europe	0.74
Podgorica	Montenegro	1	Southern Europe	0.50

Pristina	Kosovo	1	Southern Europe	0.48
Tunis	Tunisia	1	Other / Neighbourhood	0.10
Dudelange	Luxembourg	0	Western Europe	0.00
Tórshavn	Faroe Islands	0	Northern Europe	0.00
Valletta	Malta	0	Southern Europe	0.00
Victoria	Malta	0	Southern Europe	0.00

